

BANGLADESH JOURNAL OF SPORTS SCIENCE

VOLUME 8 NUMBER 2 DECEMBER 2008

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RELATIONSHIP OF SELECTED PHYSICAL AND BIO-MECHANICAL VARIABLES TO PERFORMANCE OF DISCUS THROW

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this study was to find out relationship of selected physical and bio-mechanical variables with the performance of discus throw. The subjects were five males from Lakshmibai National Institute of Physical Education (L.N.I.P.E.), Gwalior, M.P. who were state level discus throwers. The sequential photography technique was employed to record the discus technique. A motor driven, Nikon Model EM camera was used. The subjects were photographed at execution phase in sagittal plane and only the release action of discus was analyzed. From the photographs, the stick figures were prepared by using Joint-point Method, and various biomechanical variables were obtained at the moment of releasing the discus. The physical variables of each subject were taken by using an anthropometric kit and strength tests. Product Moment Correlation was calculated between the selected physical and bio-mechanical variables with the performance of discus throwers. The level of significance chosen was 0.05. The results show that a significant relationship exists between performance in discus throw and certain physical and bio-mechanical variables, whereas some variables show insignificant relationship with the performance.

Keywords: Physical variables, Biomechanical analysis, Centre of gravity.

INTRODUCTION

Biomechanics is the science concerned with the internal and external forces acting on a human body and the effects produced by these forces. The internal and external forces acting on a human body determine how the parts of that body move during the performance of a motor skill. They determine in short, what is commonly referred to as the performer's technique. There is often a wide range of techniques that might be used for the same purpose in sports and exercise—there are numerous starting techniques that may be used in sprint start; there are different methods that may be used in putting the shot; there are different starting techniques that may be used in freestyle, butterfly and breaststroke events in swimming and so on. New techniques have been

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developed as a result of scientific analysis and constant research done by the sports scientists and coaches.

Discus throw has been on the programme of Olympic Games since its inception and over the years its technique has under gone a considerable change. The distance with which a discus thrower is credited is determined by the speed, height and angle at which he (or she) releases the implement and by the aerodynamic factors that influence its flight. The speed and angle of release are determined by the magnitude and direction of the forces exerted on the discus and the distance over which these forces are applied. The height of release is governed by the athlete's body position at that instant and by his (or her) physique. A tall thrower who releases the discus from an erect position with the legs and trunk fully extended will have an advantage over other throwers who are shorter or who release the implement with their bodies in a less effective position. In addition the distance of the throw also depends upon the amount of maximum and explosive strength possessed by the thrower.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study was confined to five male discus throwers of Lakshmbai National Institute of Physical Education (L.N.I.P.E.), Gwalior. The age of the subjects ranged from 17 to 25 years. All the subjects selected for the study were state level performers. The variables chosen for the study were:

Biomechanical Variables:

1. Angle at Ankle joint
2. Angle at knee joint
3. Angle at hip joint
4. Angle at Shoulder joint
5. Angle at Elbow joint
6. Angle at Wrist joint
7. Height of release

Physical Variables:

1. *Height*
2. *Body weight*
3. *Maximum Strength*
4. *Explosive strength*
5. *Arm length*
6. *Shoulder strength*

The sequential photography technique was employed to record the discus technique. A motor driven, Nikon Model EM camera was used. The subjects were photographed at execution phase in sagittal plane and only the release action of discus was analyzed. From the photographs, the stick figures were prepared by using Joint-point Method, and various biomechanical variables were obtained at the moment of releasing the discus. The physical

variables of each subject were taken by using an anthropometric kit as well as appropriate tests for measuring different types of strength and also strength of arms and shoulders.

The performance of each subject was measured by throwing the Discus and the performance was measured from the outer edge of the throwing circle to the point where the Discus touched the ground.

PROCEDURE FOR LOCATION OF CENTRE OF GRAVITY

The following steps were followed for locating the centre of gravity (C.G.) of each subject at the time of execution of technique in discus throw.

1. On the photograph the reference points associated with each segment were marked.
2. A stick figure representation of the subjects by ruling straight lines between appropriate reference points was prepared.
3. The length of each segment line was measured and divided into appropriate ratio as indicated in Table 2 and the graphical representations have been exhibited in Figure 1:

Table 1

LOCATION OF CENTRE OF GRAVITY (C.G.) OF THE BODY SEGMENTS

S. NO	SEGMENT	C.G. LOCATION EXPRESSED AS PERCENTAGE OF TOTAL DISTANCE BETWEEN REFERENCE POINTS
1.	Head	46.48% to Vertex ; 53.6% of chin Chin Neck Intersect
2.	Trunk	38% to supra-sternal Notch; 62% to Hip Axis.
3.	Upper Arm	51.3% to shoulder Axis; 48.7% to Elbow Axis.
4.	Fore Arm	39% to Elbow Axis ; 61% to Wrist Axis
5.	Hand	82% to Wrist Axis ; 18% to Knuckle III
6.	Thigh	37.2% to Hip Axis; 62.8% to knee Axis.
7.	Calf	37.18% to Knee Axis; 62.8% to Ankle Axis.
8.	Foot	44.9% to Heel; 55.1 to Hip of Longest Toe.

Figure 1 Location of centre of gravity (c.g.) of the body segments

4. Two arbitrary axis ("oy" and "ox"), one to left and one below the stick figure were ruled out.
5. A form was prepared and in column 1, the weight of the segments was entered.
6. For each segment, the perpendicular distance from the C.G. to the line "oy" was measured and entered in the appropriate place.
7. To find out moment about "oy" the weight of each segment was multiplied by the distances of its C.G. from the line "oy" and these values were entered in column III.
8. The sum of the moment about "oy" was found out by adding the contents of on the form.
9. Imaginary line o "y" parallel to "oy" was ruled at a distance x from it (x= the sum got from step 8).
10. Steps from 5 to 9 were repeated, taking moments "ox" instead of "oy". A o "x", (x= sum got from 8th step).

The relationship of selected physical and bio-mechanical variables with the performance of discus throw was calculated by using Pearson's Product moment correlation. For testing hypothesis the level of significance was set at 0.05 level.

FINDINGS

In order to find out the relationship of selected anthropometric variables namely: Height, weight, arm length with the performance, Pearson's Product Moment Correlation were calculated between the physical variables and the performance of subjects in discus throw which was represented by the distance thrown by the subjects. The values of co-efficient of correlation are given in Table 2:

Table 2
RELATIONSHIP OF SELECTED PHYSICAL VARIABLES TO THE
PERFORMANCE IN DISCUS THROW (N =5)

S.NO	VARIABLES	CO-EFFICIENT OF CORRELATION
1.	Height	-0.20
2.	Body weight	0.45
3.	Maximum strength	0.96*
4.	Explosive strength	-0.03
5.	Arm strength	0.22
6.	Shoulder strength	0.93*

Table 2 indicates that the variables namely maximum strength and shoulder strength have significant relationship with the performance. However the body weight, explosive strength and arm length are not found highly correlated. To ascertain the relationship of these bio-mechanical variables with the performance in discus throw, the Product Moment Correlation was calculated and the results are presented in Table 3.

Table 3

RELATIONSHIP OF SELECTED BIO-MECHANICAL VARIABLES TO THE PERFORMANCE IN DISCUS THROW (N =5)

S.No	Variables	Co-efficient of correlation
1.	Ankle joint right	-0.05
2.	Ankle joint left	.74
3.	Knee joint right	.77
4.	Knee joint left	.54
5.	Hip joint right	-0.21
6.	Hip joint left	-0.39
7.	Elbow joint right	.66
8.	Elbow joint left	.59
9.	Shoulder joint right	-0.26
10.	Shoulder joint left	0.30

The table 3 indicates that the angle of ankle joint (left) and knee joint (right); the angle of elbow are not found highly correlated yet the values of correlations are sufficiently high. The graphical representation of relationship of selected bio-mechanical variables to the performance in discus throws is represented in figure 2.

Figure 2 - Relationship of selected bio-mechanical variables to performance in discus throws

DISCUSSION

The significant relationship was found between maximum strength and shoulder strength with the performance, which indicated the contribution of these variables to the discus throw. Scientists and physiologists have held the view that anthropometric measures and physical components of athletes have a lot to do with the performance. The maximum strength influences the discus thrower's performance. This may be due to the fact that with more maximum strength, the momentum gained is increased at the time of release, which enhances the performance by imparting that increased momentum to the discus. Other variables, which showed significant relationship, were shoulder strength. The bio-mechanical variables, which showed close relationship with

the performance in discus, were angles of knee and elbow joint. It indicates the importance of knee and elbow angle for efficient release of discus and an appropriate angle that helps to place the discus over the longer distance possible, as suggested by Bob Ward. The significant value of co-efficient of correlation of the releasing angle denoted the contribution of this variable for an economical release. As it is suggested by Hay, that the optimum angle of release is always somewhat less than 45, because the point at which the discus is released is some distance above the point at which it lands.

CONCLUSIONS

1. The shoulder strength has positive effect on the discus throw performance.
2. The angle of knee and the elbow angle are somewhat closely related with the performance in discus throw.
3. The body weight, explosive strength and arm length show very low relationship with the performance.
4. The angle of ankle, knee, hip and elbow joint did not show significant relationship with the performance of throwing the discus.

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